

EFFECTIVENESS OF FIELD CHEMICAL CONTROL ACTIONS AGAINST *PHILAENUS SPUMARIUS* AND *NEOPHILAENUS CAMPESTRIS* (HEMIPTERA APHROPHORIDAE) ADULT VECTORS OF *XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA* PAUCA ST53

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The need of controlling the adults of *Philaenus spumarius* (L., 1758) and *Neophilaenus campestris* (F., 1805) increased suddenly with the evidence of their attitude to transmit the phytopathogenic bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa* pauca ST53 that is responsible for Olive Quick Decline Syndrome (OQDS). From the introduction of the quarantine bacterium, several experiences targeted the knowledge of most effective active ingredients, formulations and distribution techniques for the control of adult vector. This control action is essential to avoid *X. fastidiosa* invasion and OQDS containment through the use of preventive and protective products and appropriate IPM strategies. Here we report the first results about the effectiveness of four formulated products based on different active ingredients (Sulfoxaflor, Imidacloprid, Acetamiprid, Dimethoate) belonging to 1B, 4A and 4C IRAC groups, distributed, at label rate, both by atomiser and tree injected BITE (**B**lade for **I**nfusion in **T**rees) technique. The injection method and the device allow driving all the amount recommended on the label into the plants, to get the maximum possible mortality also to reduce environmental chemical pollution and undesirable side effects. We executed the trials in experimental plots located in *X. fastidiosa*-free areas and included in an olive orchard of 10-15 years planted with FS17 *Favolosa* clone. On each plot, two opposite branches per plant were isolated by an insect-proof cage of proper mesh size to avoid *N. campestris* escaping. From 20 to 30 adult of both vectors were introduced in each net (for a total of 80-120 insect per plot) after insecticidal application, then the mortality of the two species was evaluated separately during each assessment. The formulate persistence resulted from the weekly re-introduction of the two pests species. Death counting shows that foliar application of Imidacloprid provided the highest mortality with more than 90%. Tree injection, for the same insecticide, was less effective killing 62-67% of the vectors. The other treatments applied by tree injection, gave a control from 52% to 75%, no statistically different. The insecticides distributed with the two techniques shown the persistence of over 30 days.

